

EVALUATING THE POTENTIAL OF GRIDDED PRECIPITATION DATASETS FOR HYDROLOGICAL MODELING UNDER DIFFERENT CALIBRATION SCENARIOS

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ABSTRACT: Precipitation is the most uncertain part of hydrologic cycle, and its accurate estimation requires a dense gauge network where their installation and maintenance are costly and more problematic over complex topography and remote regions. Moreover, precipitation with high spatial and temporal resolution is always recommended for streamflow prediction, which is limited for many catchments in Turkey. Hence, Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) from satellite and numerical weather prediction models or combining these sources can be an alternative to fill this shortcoming. This study aims to evaluate the consistency of four GPDs (MSWEPv2.8, CHIRPSv2.0, CFSR, and PDIR-Now) over time and space and assess their hydrological utility over a mountainous basin. The investigations are conducted at daily time step for five hydrologic years (October 2014–September 2019). Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) and Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) skill score are utilized to compare GPDs with observed precipitation directly. Among selected GPDs, MSWEPv2.8 shows the highest performance (KGE; 0.36), and PDIR-Now presents the lowest (KGE; 0.02). Furthermore, the hydrological assessment is conducted with a conceptual hydrological model under different parameterization scenarios, in which the model parameters are calibrated by observed precipitation and each GPDs individually. The simulated streamflow by observed precipitation indicates the highest Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) value (0.84) compared to GPDs. For the calibration period, selected GPDs show high reproducibility when the model is calibrated by each GPD individually.

Keywords: Gridded Precipitation Datasets, Validation, Hydrological modeling, TUW, Turkey.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water resources management is one of the challenging tasks for hydrologists and decision-makers over data-scarce catchments (Behrangi et al., 2011). Further, remote sensing techniques have made an essential contribution to water resources management and development in recent decades (Hafizi and Kalkan, 2020). Additionally, the Passive Microwave (PMW) and Infrared (IR) satellite sensor information provide an indispensable opportunity for high spatio-temporal resolution precipitation estimates (Salmani-Dehaghi and Samani, 2021). Likewise, numerical weather prediction models are able to present Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) varies in spatial and temporal and could be an alternative for filling the data scarcity over highly elevated and remote regions (Jiang et al., 2021). Considering the input and technique utilized to retrieve the precipitation amount, Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) can be classified into four distinct groups: (a) utilizing rain gauges spatial information such as Global Precipitation Climatology Centre (GPCP) (Iizumi et al., 2017), (b)

employing PMW and IR satellite sensor information into their retrospective algorithms such as Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks-Dynamic Infrared Rain Rate near-real-time (PDIR-Now) (Nguyen et al., 2020), (c) those based on reanalysis data retrieved from numerical weather prediction model output such as Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) (Saha et al., 2010), and (d) multi-source merging GPDs such as Multi-Source Weighted-Ensemble Precipitation (MSWEP) (Beck et al., 2019) and Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) (Funk et al., 2015b).

In this context, hydrological models play a significant role in streamflow simulation and prediction while providing relevant information instead of simulating every realistic scenario to understand better the basin hydrologic characteristics (Nguyen et al., 2019; Singh, 2018).

Generally, two types of validation efforts are used by several authors whereby GPDs are evaluated either by direct comparison with gauge precipitation network (meteorological evaluation) or using them as a meteorological forcing in hydrologic models for streamflow prediction (hydrological evaluation) (Bitew and Gebremichael, 2011). Furthermore, the performance of some GPDs have been quantified by several authors over Turkey (Aksu and Akgül, 2020; Amjad et al., 2020; Derin and Yilmaz, 2014; Hafizi and Sorman, 2021; Saber and Yilmaz, 2018; Uysal et al., 2021; Uysal and Şorman, 2021).

The objective of this study is to assess the spatio-temporal consistency of four GPDs (MSWEPv2.8, CHIRPSv2.0, CFSR, and PDIR-Now) by direct comparison with observed precipitation, considering the seasonal variability of precipitation in daily time step, and hydrological utility under two different calibration scenarios for five hydrologic years from October 2014 to September 2019.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area

The Çukurkişla River Basin (Figure 1) is in the headwaters of Seyhan Basin located within the longitudes 36°02' to 36°40' E and latitudes 38°40' to 38°01' N. It has a drainage area of around 1510 km², with elevation ranging from 1312 m to 2952 m and the catchment is controlled by Göksu (E18A024) stream gauging station. The basin surface is covered by bare land (35.66 %), agricultural land (34.96 %), grassland (23.86 %), forest (5.09 %), urban area (0.33 %), and wetland (0.10 %). The topographic complexity, high altitude, and snow dominant characteristics of the basin are advantageous in validating GPDs and operating hydrologic models for areas under such difficult conditions.

Figure 53. Geographical location, basin topography, and meteorological stations located around the study area

2.2. Data

In this context, four GPDs such as Multi-Source Weighted-Ensemble Precipitation (MSWEP) V2.8 (Beck et al., 2019), Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) V2.0 (Funk et al., 2015a), The climate forecast system reanalysis (CFSR) (Saha et al., 2010), and Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks-Dynamic Infrared Rain Rate near-real-time (PDIR-Now) (Nguyen et al., 2020) were selected. Moreover, observed climate data from 15 stations are provided by the General Directorate of Meteorology (GDM), and the observed streamflow data at the outlet of basin is obtained from the General Directorate of Hydraulic Works (GDHW) in Turkey.

Table 36. Properties of selected GPDs. Abbreviations in the data source represent; G, Gauge; S, Satellite; and R, Reanalysis. Abbreviation in the spatial coverage represents; L, Land.

No	Dataset name	Data source(s)	Spatial resolution	Spatial coverage	Temporal resolution	Temporal coverage
1	MSWEPv2.8	G, S, R	0.10°	Global	3-hourly	1979–Present
2	CHIRPSv2.0	G, S, R	0.05°	L-50° N/S	Daily	1981–Present
3	CFSR	R	~ 0.31°	Global	Hourly	1979–Present
4	PDIR-Now	S	0.04°	60° N/S	Hourly	2000–Present

2.3. Evaluation Approach

In this study, the modified Kling-Gupta Efficiency (Kling et al., 2012) is utilized to evaluate the reliability of GPDs by direct comparison with observed precipitation. KGE is a relatively new performance metric combining Pearson correlation coefficient (r), the ratio of bias (β), and variability ratio (γ) components (Table 2). Furthermore, the Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) skill score is used to measure the detectability strength of GPDs by considering five precipitation intensity thresholds such as no-precipitation (less than 1 mm/day), light precipitation (1–5 mm/day), moderate precipitation (5–20 mm/day), heavy precipitation (20–40 mm/day) and violent precipitation (more than 40 mm/day) (Zambrano-Bigiarini et al., 2017).

Table 37. Statistical metrics used in the study (optimal value is unity for each of Indicators).

Indicators	Mathematical statements	Remarks
Kling-Gupta Efficiency and its components	$KGE=1-[(r-1)^2+(\beta-1)^2+(\gamma-1)^2]^{0.5}$ $r=\frac{1}{n}\sum_{i=1}^n(o_n-\mu_o)(s_n-\mu_s)/(\delta_o\times\delta_s),$ $\beta=\frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o}, \quad \gamma=(\delta_s\times\mu_o)/(\mu_s\times\delta_o)$	R (Pearson correlation coefficient), β (the ratio of bias) is the ratio of estimated and observed mean, γ (Variability ratio) is the ratio of estimated and observed coefficients of variation, μ and δ are the distribution mean and standard deviation where s and o indicate estimated and observed. M (Miss); when the observed precipitation is not detected. F (False); when the precipitation is detected but not observed, H (Hit); when the observed precipitation is correctly detected, CN (Correct Negative); a no precipitation event is detected. n is the sample size of the observed or calculated streamflow. Q_i^{ob} and Q_i^{sim} present the observed and simulated streamflow, $\overline{Q_i^{ob}}$ present the mean observed streamflow.
Hanssen-Kuiper	$HK=\frac{(H\times CN)-(F\times M)}{(H+M)(F+CN)}$	
Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency	$NSE=1-\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n(Q_i^{sim}-Q_i^{ob})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n(Q_i^{ob}-\overline{Q_i^{ob}})^2}$	

Moreover, for the hydrologic utility of GPDs, Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and KGE statistical metrics are utilized. Overall, two scenarios are considered for streamflow simulation by GPDs; when the model parameters are calibrated by observed precipitation, the observed precipitation is replaced by each GPD (Scheme-1), and the model parameters are calibrated by each GPD individually. The conceptual TUW model (Parajka et al., 2007) is exploited for streamflow prediction, where its structure is similar to the HBV model. TUW model with 15 calibration parameters (Table 3) is able to simulate the runoff, snow and soil moisture, and the inputs are total daily precipitation (mm), mean

daily air temperature (°C) and daily potential evapotranspiration (mm). The PET is calculated using daily minimum and maximum near-surface air temperature (Hargreaves and Samani, 1985).

Table 38. TUW model parameter properties. Abbreviations in the process column represent; S, Snow; SM, Soil Moisture; and R, Runoff.

No	ID	Description	Units	Process	Range
1	SCF	Snow correction factor	-	S	0.9–1.5
2	DDF	Degree-day factor	mm/°C /day	S	0.0–5.0
3	Tr	Temperature threshold above which precip. is rain	°C	S	1.0–3.0
4	Ts	Temperature threshold below which precip. is snow	°C	S	-3.0–1.0
5	Tm	Temperature threshold above which melt starts	°C	S	-2.0–2.0
6	LPrat	Parameter related to the limit for potential evaporation	-	SM	0.0–1.0
7	FC	Field capacity	mm	SM	0.0–600
8	BETA	Non-linear parameter for runoff production	-	SM	0.0–20
9	cperc	Constant percolation rate	mm/day	SM	0.0–8.0
10	k0	Storage coefficient for very fast response	day	R	0.0–2.0
11	k1	Storage coefficient for fast response	day	R	2.0–30
12	k2	Storage coefficient for slow response	day	R	30–250
13	lsuz	Threshold storage state	mm	R	1.0–100
14	bmax	Maximum base at low flows	day	R	0.0–30
15	croue	Free scaling parameter	day ² /mm	R	0.0–50

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Spatio-temporal Evaluation of Daily precipitation

Figure 2 displays the mean daily precipitation and bias at the station location derived from observed precipitation and selected GPDs for the entire period (2015–2019). Considering the observed precipitation, most stations record daily precipitation ranging from 1.0 to 1.5 mm. Moreover, the southwestern part stations show higher precipitation amounts, comparatively. Overall, MSWEPv2.8 and CHIRPSv2.0 present mean daily precipitation close to observed precipitation inside the basin, while CFSR and PDIR-Now exhibit mean daily precipitation between 1.5 to 2.0 mm.

Figure 54. Mean daily precipitation at the station location derived from observed precipitation and four GPDs for the entire period. The title color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue).

Substantially, GPDs underestimate mean daily precipitation in the southwestern stations and show relatively low precipitation bias over the rest stations.

Figure 3 presents the mean daily precipitation and bias at the regional scale retrieved from observed precipitation and selected GPDs for the entire period and four seasons. In consideration of observed precipitation, the region experiences 1.4 mm mean daily precipitation for the entire period where high precipitation amount is measured during the winter and spring seasons (around 2 mm/day), and the region receives the lowest precipitation amount during the summer (0.51 mm/day) followed by autumn season (1 mm/day). All GPDs show the close precipitation pattern compared to observed for the entire period and four seasons. However, MSWEPv2.8 and CHIRPSv2.0 show less precipitation bias than the CFSR and PDIR-Now. MSWEPv2.8 consistently underestimates mean daily precipitation, but the bias is not exceeded to 0.18 mm/day. In the same way, CHIRPSv2.0 shows slightly higher precipitation estimates during the summer and autumn and underestimates precipitation during the spring and winter seasons. Among selected GPDs, CFSR shows the highest overestimation of mean daily precipitation (bias; 0.73 mm) during the winter season, followed by PDIR-Now (bias; 0.37 mm) through the autumn season.

Figure 55. Mean daily precipitation at the regional scale is derived from observed precipitation and four GPDs for the entire period and four seasons. The legend color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue)

3.2. GPDs Reliability over Time and Space

Figure 4 maps the reliability of GPDs at the grid-cell level expressed in the form of Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE), along with its Pearson correlation coefficient (r), the ratio of bias (β), and variability ratio (γ) components for the entire period (2015–2019). MSWEPv2.8 shows the highest performance by demonstrating high KGE (0.30–0.40) and correlation (0.40–0.55) over many stations. Furthermore, MSWEPv2.8 underestimates both the ratio of bias (0.75–1.00) and variability ratio (0.70–0.80). In the same way, CFSR comes with the second-best performance. However, this dataset shows poor performance over some stations (KGE less than zero) and dispersion correlation, the ratio of bias, and variability ratio. Further, CFSR presents high performance in the southern parts (KGE; 0.30–0.50, r ; 0.40–0.55). CHIRPSv2.0 shows higher performance in the eastern part stations (KGE; 0.00–0.20) than the western stations (KGE; 0.20–0.30), where it shows higher correlation in the southeastern (r ; 0.20–0.40) station compared to northwestern stations (r ; 0.10–0.20) with mostly 1.00 to 1.25 ratio of bias and 0.85 to 1.00 variability ratio appears for most stations. Finally, PDIR-Now shows the lowest performance (KGE; less than 0.20) among selected GPDs and presents weaker performance in the northwestern stations. Nevertheless, there are some discrepancies in the ratio of

bias and variability ratio. Looking at the performance of GPDs at the station location, MSWEPv2.8 exhibits promising performance followed by CFSR and CHIRPSv2.0, where PDIR-Now was not able to present reliable precipitation at the grid-cell level as the rest of the selected GPDs.

Figure 56. GPD reliability at the grid-cell level is expressed in the form of KGE and its three components for the entire period (2015–2019). The title color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue).

Figure 5 shows the consistency of GPDs at the regional scale expressed in the form of KGE and its three components (correlation, the ratio of bias, and variability ratio) for the entire period and all four seasons (spring, summer, autumn, and winter) at daily time step. All GPDs show low performance during the summer season. MSWEPv2.8 shows the highest performance considering the entire period (KGE; 0.36) and seasonal precipitation. CFSR shows the second-best performance for the entire period, and spring, summer, and autumn seasons, where this dataset shows weak performance during the winter season due to the highest bias that noticed for CFSR (bias; 1.65). Moreover, CHIRPSv2.0 demonstrated higher performance than CFSR during the winter season (KGE; 0.22). Finally, PDIR-Now figured out summer and autumn precipitation slightly better than the spring and winter seasons precipitation, and its performance is worst compared to other GPDs.

Figure 57. GPD reliability at the regional scale is expressed in the form of KGE and its three components for the entire period (2015–2019) and four seasons. The y axis color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue)

3.3. Evaluation of GPDs Detectability

Figure 6 presents the detectability strength of GPDs for five precipitation intensities at the regional scale expressed in the form of Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) skill score considers the entire period and seasonal precipitation. Overall, GPDs show high skill for precipitation events less than 1mm/day. GPDs show different detectability strengths for precipitation with specific intensity. MSWEPv2.8 exhibits higher detectability than the other GPDs. However, some GPDs such as CFSR and CHIRPSv2.0 outperform MSWEPv2.8 for heavy precipitation. CHIRPSv2.0 shows poor detectability

for light precipitation compared to selected GPDs. Moreover, GPDs show slightly higher detectability for moderate precipitation than light precipitation, where they show poor detectability for violent precipitation. The uneven detection ability of GPDs for different precipitation is partly due to the demanding classification criteria: five categories of precipitation intensities are utilized instead of the typical two classes (rain/no-rain), consistent with earlier studies concerned with GPDs validations (Hafizi and Sorman, 2022; Zambrano-Bigiarini et al., 2017).

Figure 58. GPD detectability strength at the regional scale expressed in the form of Hanssen-Kuiper (HK) skill score for five different intensities considering the entire period and four seasons. The legend color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue)

3.4. Evaluation of GPDs Ability for Streamflow Simulation

The TUW was used for streamflow simulation at the Göksu (E18A024) stream gaging station located in the outlet of Çukurkışla River Basin. Figure 7 displays the hydrographs of observed and simulated streamflow for different precipitation inputs considering two-year calibration (2015–2016) and three-year validation (2017–2019). The model parameters are calibrated in two ways. Primarily, the model parameters are calibrated by observed precipitation then the observed precipitation is replaced by each GPD (Scheme-1). Afterward, the model parameters are calibrated by each GPDs individually (Scheme-2). Among GPDs, both CFSR and PDIR-Now show high degradation (overestimation) of daily streamflow.

Figure 59. Streamflow simulation based on observed precipitation and selected GPDs for both calibration (Cal) and validation (Val) periods. The title color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue)

Figure 8 shows the result of statistical metrics computed between the observed and simulated daily streamflow for two schemes considering calibration, validation, and entire period time steps.

When the model is forced for streamflow simulation with observed precipitation, it shows pretty high ability of streamflow reproducibility for the calibration period (NSE; 0.84, KGE; 0.92) with almost no bias and variability ratio. For the validation period, simulated streamflow by observed precipitation shows lower ability (NSE; 0.38, KGE; 0.61) than the calibration period. The less efficient streamflow prediction for the validation period is partly due to the singularity of the 2019 hydrologic year, where the region received higher precipitation than the other years. In scheme-1, All GPDs (Except CFSR) show high streamflow reproducibility for the calibration period. CHIRPSv2.0 comes with the second-highest ability of streamflow simulation after observed precipitation for both calibration (KGE; 0.74) and validation (KGE; 0.56) periods. Moreover, PDIR-Now shows higher NSE (0.65) and lower KGE (0.68) than MSWEPv2.8 for the calibration period, presenting less streamflow prediction ability for the validation period. As a result, in scheme-1, CFSR presents streamflow simulation with high ratio of bias, and CHIRPSv2.0 shows the higher skill of streamflow reproducibility for both calibration and validation periods. Considering scheme-2, all GPDs show good streamflow reproducibility for the calibration period, whereas for the validation period, both CHIRPSv2.0 and MSWEPv2.8 show lower ability than scheme-1. Moreover, CFSR shows the highest KGE (0.57) and NSE (0.32) among selected GPDs in the validation period. On the other hand, PDIR-Now becomes worst in the validation period than scheme-1 and presents the highest ratio of bias (2.20) among GPDs.

Considering both schemes, multi-source merged GPDs (CHIRPSv2.0 and MSWEPv2.8) show reliable streamflow simulation than the satellite-based (PDIR-Now) and reanalysis (CFSR) GPDs in scheme-1. While in scheme-2, CFSR shows the highest performance for the validation period.

Figure 60. Statistical metrics computed between the observed and simulated daily streamflow forced by the observed precipitation (Scheme-1) and each GPDs individually (Scheme-2), respectively. The y axis color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue).

Figure 9 shows the TUW model calibrated parameters for observed precipitation and four GPDs. The green horizontal lines show the upper and lower bound of each parameter.

From the result, MSWEPv2.8 has the highest SCF value, where CFSR shows unusual K2 and Croute parameter values. Moreover, observed precipitation and four GPDs show lower cperc and bmax than these parameters' upper bound. In the same way, PDIR-Now presents the highest lsuz value among selected GPDs and observed precipitation.

Further uncertainties arising from meteorological forcing due to the existing bias in the GPDs, as noticed in section 3.2 and hydrological models, may indeed affect streamflow prediction. However, a comprehensive sensitivity/uncertainty analysis is not investigated within the scope of this study.

Figure 61 Optimum model parameters for observed precipitation and four GPDs. The legend color presents the source(s) of GPDs: satellite (blue), reanalysis (green), reanalysis, ground, and satellite (steel blue).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this context, the spatio-temporal and hydrological utility of four GPDs (MSWEPv2.8, CHIRPSv2.0, CFSR, and PDIR-Now) are investigated over Çukurkışla River Basin considering five hydrologic years (October 2014 to September 2019). The reliability of GPDs are evaluated based on 15 precipitation gauges and one stream gauging station (E18A024). The KGE, including its three components (Pearson correlation coefficient, the ratio of bias, and variability ratio), NSE, and one categorical metric (Hanssen-Kuiper skill score), are selected for meteorological and hydrological evaluation. Essential conclusions are summarized below.

- Among selected GPDs, MSWEPv2.8 presents the highest reliability of precipitation estimates over time and space where CFSR comes with the second-best performance and outperforms CHIRPSv2.0 for the entire period, spring, summer, and autumn seasons, but this dataset shows poor performance for winter season precipitation (KGE; 0.07) than CHIRPSv2.0 (KGE; 0.22). PDIR-Now, the only satellite-based precipitation dataset, shows comparatively the worst performance.
- GPDs show high detectability for low-intensity precipitation, and their detectability strength decreases by increasing precipitation intensities. However, except for CHIRPSv2.0, all GPDs show higher detectability strength for heavy precipitation than moderate precipitation, and CHIRPSv2.0 shows an unclear pattern for different precipitation intensities.
- Overall, multi-source GPDs (MSWEPv2.8 and CHIRPSv2.0) show promising ability for streamflow prediction compared to a reanalysis (CFSR) and satellite-based (PDIR-Now) precipitation datasets in scheme-1.
- In a mountainous basin, CFSR shows higher performance (KGE; 0.23) in the direct comparison with observed data, while satellite-based precipitation (PDIR-Now) shows better streamflow prediction ability for the calibration period in scheme-2.
- All GPDs show high streamflow reproducibility for the calibration period when the model is calibrated by each GPD individually.

This study confirms the outperformance of MSWEPv2.8 over other GPDs considering the meteorological evaluations. Considering both schemes for the streamflow simulation, CHIRPSv2.0 and MSWEPv2.8 seem more reliable. Moreover, reanalysis (CFSR) and satellite-based (PDIR-Now) precipitation datasets show weak performance over snow dominant region in the winter season.

Future work will include more GPDs for direct precipitation comparison and hydrologic simulations over other basins of Turkey.

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